

Extraction of L-glutamic acid using emulsion liquid membrane

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Extraction of L-glutamic acid using emulsion liquid membrane was carried out in a batch extractor. The emulsion was obtained using lubricating oil as solvent, 0.5 M HCl as internal stripping phase, IG2610E a nonionic and IG6000E an anionic surfactants as emulsifiers. Stability of emulsion was significantly affected by the volume of emulsifier and a stable emulsion was obtained for an emulsifier volume of 4% and 5% (v/v). The percentage reduction of solute in external phase depended on emulsion to external phase (*M/E*) ratio, agitator speed, and the pH of the external phase. The optimum *M/E* ratio, agitator speed, and pH for the maximum percentage reduction of solute and hence the extraction were 0.25, 150 rpm and 4.0, respectively, and under these conditions the maximum percentage reduction of solute in the external phase was 63.5. The data on percentage reduction of solute in external phase was related to agitator speed, *M/E* ratio, and pH of the external phase by regression analysis with an average absolute deviation of 15 percent.

Emulsion liquid membrane (ELM) has potential ability of separating and concentrating valuable biochemical products. This process is a less expensive and less time-consuming technique for extracting amino acids. Extraction of L-phenylalanine by ELM using facilitated anionic transport, where ELM was made of solvent, 2.0 M KCl solution as stripping phase, paranox 100 as surfactant and tricaprlyl quaternary ammonium salt (aliquat 336) as carrier in which the external phase was treated with emulsion liquid membrane in the ratio of 4 : 1 and a recovery of 74% was reported¹.

Extraction of amino acids by ELM using cationic transport, the emulsion consisting Telure 619 as solvent, 1.6 M HCl solution as stripping phase, paranox 100 as surfactant and di-2-ethylhexyl phosphoric acid as carrier where the effects of external phase pH, surfactant concentration, carrier concentration, agitation speed and stripping phase concentration on solute recovery were also studied². The extraction of L-phenylalanine by ELM using cation complexing agent, di-2-ethylhexyl phosphoric acid as carrier and reported the effect of carrier concentration and pH on the performance of extraction³. The separation of L-phenylalanine by ELM using tri-*n*-octylmethylammonium chloride as carrier and paranox 100 as emulsifier and reported the effect of agitator speed, pH and temperature on extraction⁴. The separation of L-glutamic acid by ELM using kerosene as solvent, triethanol amine as surfactant and oleic acid as carrier and reported the effect of agitator speed, emulsion to external phase ratio (*M/E*) and emulsifier concentration on the percentage reduction of solute in external phases⁵.

The present work is on the extraction of L-glutamic acid using ELM where emulsion is made of lubricating oil as solvent, 0.5 M HCl as internal stripping phase and IG2610E a nonionic surfactant and IG6000E an anionic surfactant as emulsifiers. The effect of emulsifier concentration on emulsion formation and the effect of agitation speed, *M/E* ratio and pH of the external phase on extraction performance have also been studied to optimize the operating parameters.

Results and discussion

The effect of *M/E* ratio on percentage reduction of solute is shown in Fig. 1. It is observed that as *M/E* ratio was varied from 0.16 to 0.25, the percentage reduction of solute in external phase increased for all agitator speeds. For *M/E* ratio beyond the range of 0.25 the percentage reduction in the solute decreases. This is in agreement with the findings³ for the extraction of L-phenylalanine.

From Fig. 2 it is observed that as the speed was increased from 70 to 150 rpm for a *M/E* ratio of 0.25, the maximum percentage reduction of solute was obtained as 63.5. For further increase in speed from 150 to 200 rpm, percentage recovery of solute decreased. The increase in solute recovery for agitator speeds from 70 to 150 rpm can be attributed to the increase of interfacial area of emulsion globules resulting in an increase in mass transfer area and hence an increase in percentage solute reduction. On the other hand the breakage of membrane is likely to occur at higher speeds resulting in low percentage reduction of solute. Thus the optimum agitator speed was determined as 150 rpm. Fig. 2 also shows that there is no appreciable change in percen-

Fig. 1. Effect of *M/E* ratio on percentage reduction of solute in external phase at 5% emulsifier concentration. Emulsifier concentration 5% (v/v), pH of external phase 4.0, speed of agitator (+) 70, (◆) 100, (●) 150, (▲) 175 and (*) 200 rpm

Fig. 3. Effect of pH percentage solute reduction in external phase for various *M/E* ratios at 4% emulsifier concentration. Emulsifier concentration 4% (v/v), pH (◆) 3, (●) 4, (▲) 5

Fig. 2. Effect of speed and pH on percent solute reduction in external phase. % Solute reduction vs speed (▲) 5% emulsifier conc at 4 pH, (×) 4% emulsifier conc at 4 pH. % Solute reduction vs pH (□) 4% emulsifier conc at 150 rpm

percentage reduction of solute in external phase as emulsifier concentration is varied from 4% to 5%. This indicates that for the system chosen the optimum emulsifier concentration is obtained at 4 percent.

Fig. 3 shows the effect of pH of the external phase on percentage reduction of solute in external phase and it indicates that as the pH increased from 3 to 5, the percentage reduction is maximum for a pH of 4. The reason for decrease in percentage reduction in solute at a pH of 5 is that

at high pH in the external phase, the L-glutamic acid will not dissociate as cation whereas at low pH the driving force for separation is less. Thus the optimum pH for extraction of L-glutamic acid is 4. This is in agreement with findings reported¹ for extraction of L-phenylalanine.

The following empirical relation between percentage reduction of solute in external phase to agitator speed, *M/E* ratio, and pH of the external phase has been established by regression analysis:

$$P = 23.56N^{0.1303}(M/E)^{-0.1477}H^{-0.032} \quad (1)$$

where, *H* is the pH of the external phase, *M/E* the emulsion to external phase ratio (v/v), *N* the speed of the agitator (rpm) and *P* the percentage reduction of solute in external phase. The equation represents the experimental data with an absolute deviation of 15 percent.

Conclusions

Stability of emulsion has been found to be significantly affected by the volume of emulsifier and stable emulsion was obtained for the emulsifier volume of 4 and 5% (v/v). The percentage reduction of solute in external phase was significantly affected by *M/E* ratio, agitator speed, and pH of the external phase. The optimum *M/E* ratio, agitator speed, and pH for the maximum percentage reduction of solute and hence the extraction has been found to be 0.25, 150 rpm and 4.0 respectively. The maximum percentage reduction of solute in the external phase was 63.5. An empirical equation has been obtained for percentage reduction of solute in

external phase as a function of agitator speed, M/E ratio and pH of the external phase and this equation represents the experimental data well with in an average absolute deviation of 15 percent. Further work on continuous extraction is in progress.

Experimental

The ELM was prepared initially to check stability for various emulsifier volumes in the range of 0 to 5% (v/v) with a fixed membrane to internal phase ratio of 10/7 (v/v); it was agitated for 40 min at a speed of 4000 rpm and the emulsion stability was observed for 24 h. It was inferred that emulsion was stable at an emulsifier volume of 4% and 5% for lubricating oil system. Further increase or decrease in emulsifier volume resulted in an unstable emulsion indicating 4 to 5% (v/v) as the optimum emulsifier volume.

Batch extraction was carried out in a one-liter glass vessel provided with baffles at 33°. A measured amount of emulsion was taken into the glass vessel followed by the addition of a known quantity of external phase (amino acid solution prepared as 12 g per liter) and the mixture was agitated using propeller agitator. The agitator speed was monitored by a digital tachometer. After 40 min of agitation the external phase was separated from emulsion phase and

the L-glutamic acid concentration was determined using a Jasco UV spectrophotometer. From the experiments it was observed that upto 40 min of agitation there was continuous drop in concentration of solute in the external phase and thereafter the solute concentration remained constant indicating the minimum period of agitation as 40 min.

The following parameters were also studied in batch extraction with emulsion to external phase (M/E) ratio (v/v) 0.5, 0.33, 0.25, 0.2 and 0.166, agitator speed, N (rpm) 70, 100, 150, 175, and 200, pH of the external phase 5.00, 4.00, and 3.00 and emulsifier concentration (v/v) 4 and 5%.

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